

METHODS OF QUALITY AND CONTENT ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES WITH THE HELP OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION.

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Annotation: This article discusses unique methods and techniques for organizing primary education processes in foreign countries, as well as further increasing the interest and enthusiasm of children in the educational process, that is, teaching subjects in primary grades, through the use of modern information technologies, and discusses the effectiveness of information technologies.

Key words: education, basic teachings, modern technologies, information and communication, pedagogical technologies, educational process, new methods, experiments, educational laboratories, youth psychology, character, electronic boards, slides, internet, educational materials.

Today it is very difficult to imagine our life without information technology. Of course, in the field of education in recent years, technologies have come to the main place. Because in educational processes, new information technologies combined with pedagogical technologies help to further increase the efficiency of the educational process.

The word "information" comes from the Latin word "informatio" and means "to explain".

The word "technologia" in the phrase "information technologies" means the Latin "thexnos" - **art, craft, industry** and "logos" - **science**. That is, technology means different ways of performing a task.

Information technologies are a set of methods and tools for gathering, storing, transmitting, and processing information.

As a result of the reforms in education, the quality of education in the country's schools, vocational colleges and lyceums, higher educational institutions, due to the widespread implementation of information-communication and editorial technologies, electronic textbooks and multimedia tools in the educational process, It is necessary to strengthen the educational and laboratory base of educational institutions with the most modern educational and laboratory equipment, computer equipment, and also to form an effective system of material and moral stimulation of the hard work of teachers and trainers.

The acceleration of the growth of science, technology, and information technology has brought frequent updates to the development of science and technology and information. It is known that the method of data and information transmission needs to be updated and improved. In the primary education process, it is advisable to apply such teaching methods, as a result of which students can be taught to read independently, think, work creatively with information, encourage students to think in their own way, and develop the ability to work. it is necessary to develop, to increase the interest in studying, independent learning, to develop

criticality and attitude to one's own work, to establish the ability to quickly adapt to changing working conditions.

In the primary education system, its educational technologies, including information technologies, greatly contribute to the development of the motivation to learn.

Lessons organized on the basis of information technologies should meet the needs of students according to the methods of organization and delivery methods. So these lessons are closer to the child's psyche. Achieving the goal on the basis of arousing students' interest, desire and desire to learn educational materials is a motivation, and this is a mutual interaction between the teacher and the students.

Today, it is emphasized in the world's largest scientific research that information and communication technologies have a great impact on the development of theory, creativity and reflexive thinking of students. In the memory of the students, this phenomenon, the figurative expression of the process enriches the educational material and encourages its scientific assimilation. Therefore, through the use of modern technologies, it is possible to bring educational processes to higher levels and organize the quality of education more effectively.

The scope of rapidly developing information at the world level, the application and implementation of information and editorial technologies that enable their assimilation and efficient work, is a science aimed at eliminating the problems encountered in the process of computerization of processes at all levels of educational processes. -methodical works, the need for electronic textbooks and editorial software tools from various general education subjects is increasing day by day.

The main conditions for achieving the goals envisaged in the educational process of the elementary school are: using advanced educational and information technologies from modern educational methods, using the latest educational tools and increasing the effectiveness of this process. It is to ensure that elementary school teachers have good methodological skills. As one of the modern forms of education, distance education is taking its place in all areas of the education system. In particular, educational materials on the Internet are widely used. Most of the materials available on the Internet are in the form of multimedia. For example, Elementary classes include "Who's First?", "Smart Kid" presentations, and various computer games. Elementary school students can learn mixed computer programs, which include demonstration-exercise, control-exercises and test modules, using this network of various didactic materials. It will be beneficial for him to study the rules of science and general repetition, as well as the grammar-orthographic topics given in these three options, as well as the use of various materials. Electronic textbooks can be downloaded and used in the 1st grade reading class. In it, it is possible to provide a variety of interesting visual and audio material, such as the sound-letter analysis of the word, the structure of the syllables of the word, the study of some orthograms. Bright pictures, interesting and interesting stories encourage children to increase their interest in the native language, allow them to familiarize themselves with the educational material in the form of a game, and provide ample opportunities for self-control and educational reflection. According to this manual, the differentiation of the educational process is achieved by selecting questions of different levels of complexity. In the development of thematic planning for literacy education, electronic topics and sections related to planning can be included. When developing a lesson plan, it is necessary to develop lesson plans that are appropriate for frontal, individual and group work, and the use of a computer.

In mathematics lessons, you can read and use the programs "Game problems". Various materials are provided for the various topics studied in the elementary school. Different types of puzzles of different levels of complexity encourage the development of perception and creative abilities of each student. Using computer-animated slides to solve problems increases the interest of the lesson. Their advantage lies in the fact that it is possible to focus on the issue at the time the parties want, to stop at its individual parts, to talk with the students, and to listen to their opinions. Slide films with animated problems can be used for movement in elementary grades. You can use animated pictures from the Internet to make the slides. Determining the availability of computer technologies in primary education is one of the most important indicators of using these technologies in the educational process. Taking into account the achievements in this field, it should be noted that the use of computer technology in the following aspects will be effective in the general activity of the educational institution. Prospective directions of informatization of elementary education mean the use of modern telecommunications and network information technologies. Increasing the effectiveness of the educational process of general schools and higher education institutions in using these tools will increase the possibilities. The computer expands educational resources, that is, the possibility of using various multimedia textbooks, e-books, etc. is becoming widespread. Taking this into account, today's implementation of information technologies increases the demands on the educational system, as well as informatization of the field of education in primary grades, the environment of educational activity from each educational institution requires information.

In the program "Content modernization of the continuous education system and raising the effectiveness of education to its quality level" developed within the framework of the national program of personnel training in our country, the creation of a healthy creative environment in educational institutions, promotion of the education and training process. The issues of raising the quality of teaching through the implementation of innovative, pedagogical and information technologies have been highlighted as defined tasks. The development of education brought the educational system organized in the field of informational educational multimedia tools to the world. The methods and means of solving the problems in the personnel training and education system, in the field of education and training are defined in the above-mentioned state documents. When teaching primary classes, you can mainly use game methods, interactive methods, modular technologies, non-traditional forms of lessons, and interdisciplinary integration. All these methods require children to work independently, to be able to express their thoughts freely, and to think broadly. The professional competence and level of education of the elementary school teacher, knowledge of modern educational methods are important in improving the quality of education. Unfortunately, our teachers are still unable to use information and communication technologies and multimedia tools, methodical recommendations given in audios about the educational system, to the traditional teaching system. Therefore, it should be noted that it is one of the main tasks that we should pay special attention to the study of educational methods and tools used in the teaching process, modern forms of organizing the teaching process.

References:

1. Makhamatalikizi, A. N. (2021). Necessity and Problems of Typological Study of Onomatopoeia. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(5), 101-102.
2. Aliboeva, N. (2022). The expression of comparative analysis. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 93-95.
3. Abdukakhhorovna, J. M. (2021). Scientific Views on the Development of the Anthropocentric Paradigm in Linguistics. *JournalNX*, 7(07), 20-21.
4. Abdukahhorovna, J. M. (2021). History of the study of introductions and entries in Russian linguistics. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 11(1), 238-240.
5. Abdukakhhorovna, J. M. (2020, June). THE SYSTEM OF PHONETIC GAMES IN THE TEACHING OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 70-71).
6. Жураева, М. А. (2016). ВНЕКЛАССНАЯ РАБОТА В СИСТЕМЕ НЕПРЕРЫВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ (ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЙ КВН). *Вестник современной науки*, (2-2), 94-96.
7. Abdukahharovna, J. M. (2022). ANALYSIS OF THE SEMANTIC PECULIARITIES OF THE WORDS OF MASTERING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN THE UZBEK LITERARY LANGUAGE. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 110-112.
8. Soliev, O. (2022). GENERAL CONCEPTS ABOUT EDUCATIONAL LAWS AND METHODS OF EFFECTIVE USING THEM IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(4), 448-452.
9. Ахмедова, Р. М., & Адилов, Ф. А. (2016). Подготовка специалистов в отрасли ремесленного производства в 20-х годах XX века. *Ученый XXI века*, (5-4 (18)), 62-64.
10. Ахмедова, Р. (2020). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ДАСТЛАБКИ ШИФО МАСКАНЛАРИНИНГ ВУЖУДГА КЕЛИШИ (ФАРФОНА ВОДИЙСИ МИСОЛИДА). *ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ*, (SI-1№ 1).
11. Mukimovna, A. R. (2020, December). History of children's sanatorium resorts in Uzbekistan (1930-1953). In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 311-314).
12. BURIYEV, S., МАХКАМОВА, D., & SHERIMBETOV, V. (2020). Ekologiya va atrof muhit muhofazasi. O'quv qo'llanma. T-innovatsiya ziyo.
13. Ахмедова, Р. М. (2022). From the history of the socio-material situation of the population of Uzbekistan (on the example of 1920-1940). *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(09), 243-247.
14. Ahmedova, R., & Muxtorova, M. (2023). FARG'ONA VODIYSIDAGI SHIFO MASKANLARINING VUJUDGA KELISHI TARIXIDAN ("CHORTOQ" SIHATGOXI MISOLIDA). *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).
15. Ahmedova, R., & Muxtorova, M. (2023). O'ZBEKISTON SANATORIY-KURORTLARI DAVOLASH ISHLARIDAGI AYRIM MUAMMOLAR TARIXI. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).
16. Ahmedova, R., & Shokirova, A. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF REFORMS IN THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS LEGAL FRAMEWORK OVER THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(5), 1112-1116.
17. Mukimovna, A. R., Asqarovna, Q. S., & Sodiqovich, K. Q. (2022). HISTORY OF SOME PROBLEMS IN TREATMENT WORKS OF SANATORIUMS AND SPAS OF UZBEKISTAN. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(7).
18. Abdukahhorovna, Z. M. (2022). Lexical Polysemy of the Russian Language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 22, 77-81.

19. Abdukahharovna, J. M. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE-SPEECH COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(02), 8-11.
20. Abdukahharovna, J. M. (2022). Working On Words With An Untested Unstressed Vowel At The Root Of A Word In Elementary School. Journal of Positive School Psychology, 145-149.
21. Abdukahharovna, J. M. (2022). PRIORITIES OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN. ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 113-119.
22. Soliyev, O. (2022). PEDAGOGIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA ILMIY-TADQIQOT METODLARIDAN FOYDALANISH. Science and innovation, 1(B6), 38-42.
23. Алибаева, Н. М. (2017). Бадий матнларда эмоционал гаплар. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 2-3.
24. Isoqjonova, D., & Aliboyeva, N. (2020). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA INTENSIVLIK SEMANTIKASINI IFODALOVCHI XARAKAT FE'LLARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI. In МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ (pp. 363-366).
25. қизи Алибоева, Н. М., & Хошимов, Д. (2022). Тақлидий сўзларни типологик ўрганиш муаммолари. Science and Education, 3(3), 380-382.
26. Madumarov, T., & Ogli, G. O. R. (2023). FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM). Educational sacrifices, 02-05.